

THE ROLE OF TEACHING HUMANITIES IN GOVERNING THE FISCAL ECONOMICS OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation. the role of humanities in economics may not seem as valuable as some other subjects which have drawn much attention (e.g. finance, architecture and medicine). The disciplines that are “in trend” usually seen as decisive or rewarding. Without going into the underlying reasons why those (above listed) subjects are preferred more, let’s see why humanities are not as preferable as other more common disciplines. The significance of humanities in enhancing tax governance and better attitude towards money is indispensable. In this paper, two angles why prospective students are not picking humanities and why higher education is not offering many courses on humanities will be discussed. Finally, the significance of humanities in terms of fiscal economics of Uzbekistan will be considered with some arguments.

Key words: Finance, rewarding, humanities, governance, economics, curriculum, financially prosperous, tax specialist, linguistics, social contentment, counterpart

If we take a deeper look at the “modern” curriculum of higher education, it can clearly be witnessed that humanities are rare subjects on the current curriculum. A similar view was pointed out by Duturayeva D (2021) daryo.uz. She says that some fields of study have more attention as they have been entitled as financially prosperous. This is where the reason for lack of attention to humanities comes from. However, it is not by far the only cause of little recognition of humanities. She continues by saying, “trendy” subjects promise faster reward than humanities. She puts a seriousness of humanities as the decisive factor in having a critical thinking. Let’s see what is the relationship between critical thinking and taxation. With the right attitude towards taxation and conscious decision making, both tax payers and collectors can communicate effortlessly. Moreover, thinking out of the box also eases the process of financial state of Uzbekistan.

I would as well add importance of history as one of the humanities` subjects, which was once put into a saying “Without the historical memory, there is no future” I. Karimov. All the mistakes made in the past serve as lessons for the future. Keeping this in mind, humanities are in the need for more teaching and learning. Tax governance is managed better when people working in this sphere have an up-to-date knowledge by being equipped with past generation`s experience. Not only history makes us realize what was done successfully but also it gives us the clues about the mistakes made in the past. Keeping this in mind, the one subject of humanities, history should be paid more attention in higher education institutions. Fiscal management is one of the key determining factors in a country which goes beyond the taxation. Taxes are as we already know the resource for education healthcare and other public services. Thus, knowledgeable tax specialists ought to study history among other humanities.

Linguistics and language as another component of humanities have attracted more attention in education generally. All faculties of Fiscal now offer at least 2-years of “intensive” language learning. The aim here is to enable the prospective tax service professionals to be flexible at gaining the knowledge to successfully work in the tax collecting service. With more languages on board, future tax staff will access new up-to-date data. On the other end of the angle, Uzbekistan was put on 88 place among 112 countries` in the rating of English proficiency level (EF English Proficiency Index, 2021). In the past two years prior to 2021, level of proficiency had grown 6 countries above (Uzbekistan was on the 94 place by 2019). It means the change in curriculum is giving its first positive results. The fiscal management is in need of professionals with high language level. Better language leads to better communication not only within the country but beyond the country`s borders with foreign counterparts on the same field (tax service). Humanity has evolved mainly out of communication and passing knowledge from generation to generation. In other words, what our ancestors had known would later be passed to upcoming generation. If the language is the main means of communication, its value is just priceless. Having more languages can be a lot more beneficial than just knowing one single. Therefore, the current trend of learning language and all the opportunities available for language learners should be maintained for the years coming.

In the Fiscal management, the significance of sociology (as one sphere of humanities) is as essential as other disciplines listed above. Sociology is taught at some higher education establishments but not all. It seems that this is enough to give this amount of credit to sociology. However, if a close look is given to this subject, the scope of this discipline becomes clear to unaided eye. Let`s only focus on the economic significance of sociology. Economy is balanced when the law is in strict use. As well as these, sociology goes into social satisfaction. What is the relationship between social happiness and Fiscal management? First, when society is content at home or at workplace, they are willing to pay taxes on time without procrastination. Secondly, social satisfaction means better relationship, less crime, more gratitude when people work, thus higher efficiency. On top of that, being in a higher mood, energizes people which ultimately contributes to higher output at work. In recent years, sociology has focused on economics, too. Economics and Fiscal governance are two inseparable parts of any country or society. Social contentment and financial governance are I think are two highly important components of prosperous country. Happy residents make up a happy country. Having realized the scope of sociology, we can now say that sociology also one sphere of humanities which needs more attention.

So far in this paper, the role and importance of the disciplines like history, linguistics and sociology has been pointed out. Now, let`s have a look at psychology as one branch of humanities and what link it has with Fiscal management in Uzbekistan. The roots of relationship between psychology and economics go to the year of 1991 (Drakopoulos, 1991; Warneryd, 1994). Prior to this period, there was no or very little interest in linking psychology and economics. It was rightfully pointed out in the article “The relationship between psychology and economics: Insights from the history of economic thought” (A. Stavros and K. Ioannis, 2017), that learning human behavior helps us to better understand “economic matters”. Fehr and Schmidt (1999) stated that learning psychology can shed light into the human decision making ability. Better understanding of cognitive processes can explain

cooperation, risk taking and intertemporal preference (Camerer, Loewenstein and Prelec, 2005). This notion reinforces the abovementioned idea that psychology gives us clearer view on how people communicate economically. Ultimately, economic decision making is directly related with Fiscal management. If we have deep comprehension of economic interaction, cooperation becomes more straightforward. Tax payers and tax collectors should communicate effectively to reach satisfactory outcome. Professionals currently working in Fiscal system definitely need to have a higher level of human interaction skills to successfully carry out their duties. In addition to working staff of Fiscal governance, prospective tax employees are as well in need of psychological expertise. The students aspiring to become tax service staff are not always taking courses in psychology. Having said this, it is advisable to add one more discipline “psychology” out of humanities to put even better interpersonal interaction between tax collectors and tax payers.

To finalize all the arguments above, one can easily see how much of importance humanities hold in Uzbekistan Fiscal management. It is also noteworthy that in this paper humanities were examined with the aim of discovering this set of subjects` positive impact on Fiscal governance. One can as well argue that there are other subjects that play equal role. Aim of this work was not to compare what field of study is superior or inferior, rather focused approach has been utilized here to rediscover or draw more attention to humanities as something which has some or even profoundly positive effect on Fiscal management in Uzbekistan.

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